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Research Article

**A STUDY ON RELEASE BEHAVIOR OF NATURAL AND
SYNTHETIC POLYMERS****Amrish B Kantikar¹, Dr.Abdul Sayeed², Md Ather Ahmed Abid¹
Shakeel Ahmed Siddiqui¹.**¹ Assistant professor, KCT College of Pharmacy, Kalaburagi-585104.² Professor, MESCO College of Pharmacy Hyderabad-5000006.**Abstract:**

In the pharmaceutical dosage forms several approaches are available to include the loading dose of a drug to the maintenance dose of a drug for sustained action. A novel approach for having the loading dose and maintenance dose in a tablet is the formulation of drugs in Matrix tablets. By using Matrix tablet system, it makes possible to design extended release preparation with an immediate release quantity in one layer and extended release proportion in the second, thus maintaining a prolong blood level.

Aceclofenac is belongs to the category of non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), which has the biological half-life 2-4 hrs, and bioavailability of 15 %, so attempt to make Aceclofenac bi-layer matrix tablets to sustained the drug release for extended period of time.

In the present work an attempt has been made to prepare matrix tablets of aceclofenac in which one layer was sustained release layer and other layer was immediate release layer. The sustained release layer was made by using various synthetic and natural polymers.

The synthetic polymers CMC, HPMC and natural polymer delonix regia seed gum (DRSG) were used in the different concentrations. All the tablets were prepared by wet granulation method. The prepared granules and tablets were evaluated for various pre compression and post compression parameters like angle of repose, bulk density, tapped density, hausner's ratio, carr's index, hardness, thickness, weight variation, drug content, in-vitro drug release, drug-polymer interaction by IR and DSC studies and short term stability study. The prepared tablets showed the hardness between 6.5 ± 0.10 kg/cm² and 7.0 ± 0.30 kg/cm², weight variation in the range 307 ± 0.58 mg to 326 ± 0.23 mg which is below $\pm 7.5\%$, friability below $>1\%$ and drug content in between 95.51 ± 1.75 to $100.03 \pm 1.23\%$. All the formulations displayed zero order release kinetics 'r' values from 0.926 to 0.998 for all the formulations. Higuchi and Peppas data reveals that the drug released by non - fickian diffusion mechanisms.

In-vitro drug release study shows near about 21 % drug release within first two hrs. because of immediate release layer and 99.25%, 98.34% and 98.7 % drug release at the last of 24th hr. in the formulation AHII, ADI and AHC which contains 40%HPMC, 30% Delonix regia seed gum and 24%HPMC and 24% DRS gum respectively, which found to be most promising.

From the IR and DSC studies results reveals that there is no interaction between drug and any excipients. Stability study results reveals that there is no change in the drug content in the prepared tablets.

Keywords: Matrix tablets, Aceclofenac, CMC, HPMC, Delonix regia seed gum.

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INTRODUCTION:

For many years, oral drug delivery continues to be the preferred route of pharmaceutical administration of many drug substances. Approaches and technologies in the area of modified release oral drug delivery has been developed to extend the release of drug over a number of hours, an effect accomplished either by combining the drug with release retardant materials to form a matrix core or applying release modifying film coatings to cores containing the drugs. For developing matrix tablet, various materials like waxes, hydrophilic or hydrophobic polymers and gums have been employed in the formulation. Among these polymers, the use of hydrophilic matrices has been extremely popular in controlling the release of drug from solid dosage forms. Among the hydrophilic polymers, swellable and hydrophilic property of hydroxyl propyl methylcellulose (HPMC) has been paid considerable attention for the preparation of matrix tablets as sustained release formulations of various drugs. Natural gums were also successfully utilized as release retarding agents, as the natural gums are cost effective, non-toxic, biodegradable, and easily available and offer flexibility in manufacturing.

In the pharmaceutical dosage forms several approaches are available to include the loading dose of a drug to the maintenance dose of a drug for sustained action. A novel approach for having the loading dose and maintenance dose in a tablet is the formulation of drugs in multilayered / tablets. By using multilayer or bi-layer tablet system, it makes possible to design extended release preparation with an immediate release quantity in one layer and extended release proportion in the second, thus maintaining a prolong blood level. The immediate release portion will disintegrate rapidly after ingestion, thus providing the initial dose of medication for immediate on set of action whereas the matrix layer remains intact during most of the time of its passes through the intestine, while dissolving slowly from its exposed phases in this passage, which helps to maintain the blood level that initially reached¹.

The design of sustained release delivery system is subject to several variables of considerable importance. Among these, route of drug delivery, the type of delivery system, the disease being treated, the patient, length of therapy and the properties of the drug. The drug should be stable in the gastrointestinal tract as the sustained release systems release their contents over entire length of gastrointestinal tract. Therefore, drugs degraded by the acid environment of the stomach or degraded by

the basic environment of intestine are unsuitable for formulation into sustained release dosage forms.

Two layer tablets may be designed for sustained release – one layer for the immediate release of the drug and second layer for extended release thus maintaining a prolonged blood level. The pharmacokinetic advantage relies on the criterion that, drug release from the fast releasing layer leads to a sudden rise in blood concentration. However, the blood level is maintained at steady state, as the drug is released from sustaining layer². Layers may be colored differently to identify the product. The weight of each layer can be accurately controlled in contrast to putting one drug of a combination product in a sugar coating³.

Generally, conventional controlled-release dosage forms delay the release of Drugs and do not provide a rapid onset of action after oral administration.

Hence, the layered tablets offer a pharmacokinetic advantage over conventional controlled-release dosage forms as the drug is quickly released from the fast-release layer leading to rapid rise of drug plasma concentration followed by continuation of drug release from the sustained-release layer. This release pattern is required for successful treatment in many therapies, primarily when maximum relief needs to be achieved as soon as possible, and is followed by a sustained-release phase to avoid repeated drug administration⁴.

The basic goal of therapy is to achieve a steady state drug in blood level for an extended period of time. The design of proper dosage regimens is an important element in accomplishing this goal. Sustained release, sustained action and prolonged action controlled release, extended action, timed release depot and repository dosage forms are terms used to identify drug delivery system than are designed to achieve a prolonged therapeutic effect by continuously releasing medication over an extended period of time after administration of single dose. In the case of injectable dosage forms, this period may vary from day to months. In the case of orally administered dosage forms, this period is measured in hours and critically depends on the residence time of the dosage form in the gastrointestinal tract. The term controlled release has been associated with those systems from which therapeutic agents may be automatically delivered at predetermined rates over a long period of time.

Products of this type have been formulated for oral injectable⁵ and topical use and inserts for placement

in the body cavities.

Controlled-release drug administration means not only prolonged duration of drug delivery as in sustained release, but also implies the predictability and reproducibility of drug release kinetics. Optimal therapy of a disease requires the efficient delivery of active drugs to the tissue or organs that need treatment. In recent years' considerable attention has been stressed on the development of controlled drug delivery system for convenience and patient compliance⁶. Sustained release drug delivery system, which is mainly consist of two parts: an immediately available dose and a sustaining part. The immediately available dose is normally directly added to the sustaining part of the table tor alternatively is incorporated in the tablet coating with the sustaining portion in the core of the tablet i.e., a portion (initial priming dose) of the drug is released immediately in order to achieve the desired therapeutic response promptly. There mining dose of the drug (maintenance dose) is then released slowly there by resulting in therapeutic drug / tissue level, which is a prolonged but not maintained constant⁷.

Sustained release systems include any drug delivery system that achieves slow release of drug over an extended period of time. If the system is successful in maintaining constant drug levels in the blood or target tissue. It is considered as a controlled release system. If it is unsuccessful of this day never the less extends the duration of action over that achieved by conventional delivery. It is considered as a prolonged release system⁸.

The oral route of administration for sustained release systems has received greater attention because of more flexibility in dosage form design.

The design of oral sustained release delivery systems are subjected to several interrelated variables of considerable importance. Such as the type of delivery system, the disease being treated, the patient, the length of therapy and the properties of the drug.

OBJECTIVE

Need of the study:

For many years, oral drug delivery continues to be the preferred route of pharmaceutical administration of many drug substances. Approaches and technologies in the area of modified release oral drug delivery has been developed to extend the release of drug over a number of hours, an effect accomplished either by combining the drug with release retardant materials to form a matrix core or applying release modifying film coatings to cores containing the

drugs. For developing matrix tablet, various materials like waxes, hydrophilic or hydrophobic polymers and gums have been employed in the formulation. Among these polymers, the use of hydrophilic matrices has been extremely popular in controlling the release of drug from solid dosage forms.

Among the hydrophilic polymers, swellable and hydrophilic property of hydroxy propyl methyl cellulose (HPMC) has been paid considerable attention for the preparation of matrix tablets as sustained release formulations of various drugs. Natural gums were also successfully utilized as release retarding agents, as the natural gums are cost effective, non-toxic, biodegradable, and easily available and offer flexibility in manufacturing.

In the pharmaceutical dosage forms several approaches are available to include the loading dose of a drug to the maintenance dose of a drug for sustained action. A novel approach for having the loading dose and maintenance dose in a tablet is the Formulation of drugs in multilayered/ Matrix tablets. By using multi layer or Matrix tablet system, it makes possible to design extended release preparation with an immediate release quantity in one layer and extended release proportion in the second, thus maintaining a prolong blood level. The immediate release portion will disintegrate rapidly after ingestion, thus providing the initial dose of medication for immediate onset of action where as the matrix layer remains intact during most of the time of its passes through the intestine, while dissolving slowly form its exposed phases in this passage, which helps to maintain the blood level that initially reached.

Aceclofenac is used for the treatment of pain and inflammation in osteoarthritis, rheumatoid arthritis, and ankylosing spondylitis. This drug works by blocking the effect of cyclo oxygenase (COX) enzymes that make chemical prostaglandins at sites of injury or injury causing pain, swelling, and inflammation. After oral administration, aceclofenac is rapidly and completely absorbed as unchanged drug. Peak plasma concentrations are reached approximately 1.25 to 3.00 hours following ingestion. Aceclofenac penetrates in to the synovial fluid, where the concentrations reach approximately 57% of those in plasma. Elimination half-life is 4 hours following single or multiple dose.

Hence, in the present research investigation attempt was made to formulate bi- layer matrix tablets of aceclofenac by using synthetic polymers like HPMC, CMC and sodium alginate and natural polymers like

delonix regia seed gum.

Objectives of the study:

The present research investigation is planned with the following objectives.

To formulate the Matrix tablets of Aceclofenac

1. To investigate the performance of several hydrophilic matrix systems prepared by HPMC, CMC and Delonix regia seed gum in controlling the release of Aceclofenac.
2. To evaluate the formulation with respect to various physical parameters.
3. To evaluate the formulation with respect to content uniformity, *in-vitro* release study, drug excipient interaction studies (IR & DSC).
4. The drug, release data will be fit in to different kinetic model.
5. Stability study will be carried out on the design formulation according to ICH guide line.

METHODS:

SOLUBILITY STUDIES

The solubility of aceclofenac was done in 0.1 M hydrochloric acid (pH 1.2), Phosphate buffer 6.8 pH, Phosphate buffer 7.4 pH, Water and Methanol. An excess amount of the drug was added to 50 ml-

stoppered conical flasks. The flasks were shaken mechanically at $37\text{-C} \pm 0.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 24 hours. After another 2 days of equilibrium, aliquots were withdrawn and filtered (0.22- μm pore size filter paper). Then, the filtered samples were diluted with respective solvents. The absorbance of final solutions was measured spectrophotometer at 271 nm and concentration of drug was calculated.

Determination of λ_{max} of Aceclofenac.

A 12mcg/ml of Aceclofenac in phosphate buffer pH7.4 was scanned in UV range between 200-400 nm. Aceclofenac showed maximum absorbance at 271nm in phosphate buffer pH 7.4.

Standard calibration curve for Aceclofenac.

Preparation of standard graph:

Standard graph for the drug Aceclofenac was done separately in pH 1.2 acidic buffers and pH 7.4 phosphate buffers. Table 1 and table 2 shows the concentrations of Aceclofenac in pH 1.2 acidic buffers and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer and the respective absorbance.

The figure 1 and figure 2 shows calibration curve of Aceclofenac in pH 1.2 acidic buffer and pH 7.4 phosphate buffer.

Table1: Data for standard curve of Aceclofenac in pH 1.2 acidic buffer at 271nm.

Concentration	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.161
4	0.297
6	0.446
8	0.601
10	0.747

Fig1: Standard curve of Aceclofenac in pH 1.2 acidic buffer solutions at λ_{max} 271nm.

Table2: Data for standard curve of Aceclofenac in pH7.4 phosphate buffer at 271 nm.

Concentration	Absorbance
0	0
2	0.160
4	0.311
6	0.455
8	0.614
10	0.775

Fig2: Standard curve of Aceclofenac in pH 7.4phosphate buffer solutions at 271nm.**FORMULATION DESIGN:****Preparation of Matrix tablet:****Formulation of sustained release layer**

Accurately weighed quantity of Aceclofenac, and required quantity polymer were taken in mortar and mixed. The powders were mixed with the sufficient quantity of PVP K 30 in distilled water until wet mass formed. The cohesive mass obtained was pass through sieve # 16 and the granules were dried in an oven at 50⁰ C for an hr. The dried granules were

again sieved through sieve # 22. The granules were mixed with required quantities of talc and magnesium stearate. The required amount of granules for sustained release layer was compressed into tablets in the single punch tablet machine using 8 mm round and convex punches. Over this compressed layer, required quantity of fast releasing layer powder was placed and compressed lightly to form a Matrix tablet.

Table: 3.Formulation of Aceclofenac tablets using HPMC, CMC & delonix regia seed gum (DRSG).

Ingredients (mg/tab)	Formulations										
	AC I	AC II	AC III	AH I	AH II	AH III	AD I	AD II	AD III	ADC	AHC
Aceclofenac	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100
Lactose	110	90	70	110	90	70	110	90	70	70	70
CMC	80	100	120	-	-	-	-	-	-	60	-
HPMC	-	-	-	80	100	120	-	-	-	-	60
DRSG	-	-	-	-	-	-	80	100	120	60	60
PVPK-30	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6	6
Mg.stearate	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Talc	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total weight	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300	300

Evaluation:**1. Evaluation parameters for Matrix tablets:****Pre-Compression Parameters:**

The flow properties of the physical mixture were studied by measuring the angle of repose and Carr's index of physical mixture.

Angle of Repose (θ)⁹:

Angle of repose is an indication of the frictional force existing between the particles. This is the maximum angle possible between the surface of a pile of physical mixture and the horizontal plane.

This is given by:

$$\tan \theta = h / r \quad \text{or } \theta = \tan^{-1} (h / r) \text{ Where,}$$

θ = The angle of repose.

h=The height of the pile in cm.

r=The radius of the pile at the base in cm.

The physical mixture was allowed to flow through the funnel that can be rise vertically until a maximum cone height 'h' was obtained. The angle of repose was then calculated by measuring the height and the radius of the heap at the base. The flow property can be improved by adding lubricant (Magnesium stearate).

Bulk Density¹⁰ :

An accurately weighed quantity of powder, which was previously passed through sieve#40 and carefully poured in to graduated cylinder. Then after pouring the powder in to graduated cylinder the powder bed was made uniform without disturbing. Then the volume was measured directly from graduation mark on the cylinder as ml. the volume measure was called as the bulk volume and the bulk density is calculated by using following formula.

Bulk density=Weight of powder/ volume of packing

Tapped density¹¹ :

A quantity of 2 gm of powder from each formula was introduced into a 10 ml measuring cylinder. After a initial volume was observed, the cylinder was allow to fall under its own weight on the hard surface from the height of 2.5cm at two second intervals. The tapping was continued until no further change in the volume was noted. The tapped density was calculated by using following formula.

Tapped density=weight of powder/tapped volume of packing.

Hausner's ratio¹² :

Hausner's ratio is an indirect index of ease of power flow. It is calculated by the following formula.

$$\text{Hausner's ratio} = D_t/D_b$$

Where D_t is tapped density and D_b is bulk density. Lower Hausner's ratio (<1.25) indicates better flow properties than higher ones (>1.25).

Carr's index (C.I.)¹³ :

It helps in measuring the force required to break the friction between the particles and the hopper. It is expressed in % and given by

$$\frac{D_t - D_b}{D_t} \times 100$$

Where, D_t =The tapped density of the physical mixture.

D_b =The bulk density of the physical mixture.

The flow property can be improved by adding glidants (e.g.Talc).

Post-compression parameters:

The tablets were subjected to the following tests:

- Hardness and Friability.
- Thickness.
- Weight variation.
- Drug content
- *In vitro* release profile.

Hardness¹⁴:

The resistance of tablets to shipping or breaking under the condition of storage, transportation and handling before the uses depends on its hardness. The Hardness of the tablet was determined using a Monsanto Hardness tester. It is expressed in kg / cm^2

Friability (F)¹⁵ :

Friability is the measure of tablet strength. The Friability of the tablet was determined using Roche friabilator. It is expressed in percentage (%). 20 tablets were initially weighed (W_{initial}) and transferred into the friabilator. The friabilator was operated at 25 rpm for 4 mins. The tablets were weighed again (W_{final}). The % friability was then calculated by,

$$F = \frac{W_{\text{initial}} - W_{\text{final}}}{W_{\text{initial}}} \times 100$$

W_{initial}

Thickness¹⁶:

Three tablets were selected randomly from each batch and the thickness was measured using vernier caliper and expressed in mm.

Weight variation¹⁷ :

To study the weight variation, twenty tablets from each formulation were selected at random and determine their average weight. Not more than two of the individual weights may deviate from the average weight by more than the percent deviation and none should deviate by more than twice that percentage (Limit for not more than 130 to 324mg is 7.5 %).

Drug Content¹⁷ :

Ten tablets were weighted and powdered. Powder equivalent to 40 mg of Aceclofenac was transferred in the 100 ml volumetric flask and 70 ml phosphate buffer having pH 7.4 is added. Then flask was shaken for 10 min. Finally the volume was made up to the

mark with phosphate buffer. Then it was analyzed in U.V. spectrophotometer at 271nm using phosphate buffer pH7.4 as blank and the% drug content was estimated using the following formula.

$$\text{Drug content} = \frac{\text{Absorbance} \times \text{Dilution Factor}}{\text{Slope}} \\ \% \text{ Drug Content} = \frac{\text{Drug Content} \times 100}{\text{Label Claim}}$$

IN-VITRO DRUG RELEASE STUDIES:

Dissolution study was carried out for Matrix tablet to measure the release rate of drug form the dosage form.

Dissolution medium: 900 ml of pH1.2 buffer for first 2hr, and followed by pH7.4 buffer for 22 hrs.

Apparatus: USP apparatus II (Paddle type for tablets) Rotation speed: 100 rpm

Temperature: 37°C±0.5°C Sampling time: Every 15min. for first 2 hr. and every hour up to 24 hr.

Procedure:

The *In-vitro* release profile was carried by maintaining the above condition, the formulation was placed in 900ml of pH1.2 buffer for first 2hr and in pH7.4 for remaining 22 hr, 5ml of the sample was withdrawn at a particular time interval and replaced with same fresh dissolution media. The withdrawn samples were analyzed and the amount of the Aceclofenac released was determined by UV absorption method at 271 nm.

DRUG-POLYMER INTERACTION STUDIES:

FTIR Study:

There is always a possibility of drug-polymer interaction in any formulation due to their intimate contact. Compatibility studies were carried out to know the possible interactions between Aceclofenac and excipients used in the formulation. Physical mixtures of drug and excipients were prepared to study the compatibility. The technique employed in this study is FTIR spectroscopy. FTIR spectroscopy is one of the most powerful analytical techniques, which offers the possibility of chemical identification. The FTIR spectra of Aceclofenac and formulations were obtained by KBr pellet method.

DSC Study:

The physicochemical compatibilities of the drug and the used excipients were tested by differential scanning calorimetric (DSC) analysis. DSC thermo grams of the drug alone and drug-excipient physical mixtures were derived from a DSC with a thermal analysis data station system, computer, and plotter interface. The instrument was calibrated with an indium standard. The samples (2-4 mg) were heated (0°C-300°C) at a constant scanning speed (10-C/min) in sealed aluminum pans, using nitrogen as purging gas.

SELECTION OF THE FORMULATION FOR STABILITY STUDIES:

From the evaluation of the formulations, the

formulations AH II, AD I, ADC and AHC. Were selected for the stability studies as these formulations released the drug at the desired release profile for 24 hrs.

STABILITY STUDIES:

Stability studies were performed at temperature 45°C and 75%RH over a period of three months on the selected matrix tablets formulations. Sufficient number of tablets (10) were packed in Amber colored screw capped bottles and kept in stability chambers maintained at 45°C and 75%RH. Samples were taken at intervals of 30days for the drug content estimation, which is shown in table 22.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION:

Solubility study data of Aceclofenac in different solvents/buffers as follows.

Solubility of pure drug in different buffers, water and methanol were done in order to find out the appropriate dissolution medium. From the solubility study data it is clear that, the drug has more solubility in 0.1N HCL and phosphate buffers. 0.1NHCL and phosphate buffer 7.4 PH were selected as dissolution medium, as these can medium the perfect sink conditions.

Table4: Solubility study data for Aceclofenac.

S.No.	Solvent	Solubility (µg/ml)
1	Phosphate buffer 7.4pH	4.315
2	Phosphate buffer 6.8pH	3.915
3	0.1NHCl	3.526
4	Water	2.751
5	Methanol	1.887

Characterization of aceclofenac tablets

Pre compression parameters

The aceclofenac granules ready for compression containing drug and various excipients were subjected for pre-compression parameters to study the flow properties of granules, to achieve uniformity of tablet weight. The results of all the preformulation parameters are given below.

Angle of repose (θ):

The data obtained from angle of repose for all the formulations were found to be in the range of 21.32 and 28.72. All the prepared formulations showed the angle of repose less than 30°, which reveals good flow property.

Densities:

Loose bulk density (LBD) and tapped bulk density (TBD) for the blend was performed. The loose bulk density and tapped bulk density for the entire formulation blend varied from 0.616 gm/cm³ to 0.757 gm/cm³ and 0.701 gm/cm³ to 0.865

gm/cm³respectively.

Carr's consolidation index:

The results of Carr's consolidation index or compressibility index (%) for the entire formulation

blend ranged from 12.26 % to 15.42 %.

Hausner's ratio:

Hausner's ratio of entire formulation showed between 1.10 and 1.19 indicates better flow properties.

Table 5: Pre-compressional parameters Aceclofenac Matrix Tablets.

Formulation Code	Parameters				
	Bulk Density (gm/ml) ±SD,n=3	Tapped Density (gm/ml) ±SD,n=3	Angle of Repose(θ) ±SD,n=3	Carr's Index (%) ±SD,n=3	Hausner's Ratio ±SD,n=3
AC I	0.732±0.05	0.816±0.09	28.72±0.9	13.74±0.92	1.13±0.07
AC II	0.745±0.01	0.809±0.11	23.17±1.1	12.98±1.28	1.14±0.01
AC III	0.719±0.06	0.783±0.26	25.64±0.7	12.47±1.32	1.18±0.02
AHI	0.757±0.03	0.865±0.27	27.60±1.2	12.52±1.46	1.14±0.03
AHII	0.730±0.02	0.834±0.51	23.94±1.7	12.47±1.11	1.10±0.05
AHIII	0.616±0.04	0.701±0.34	24.41±1.4	12.26±1.09	1.14±0.01
ADI	0.687±0.04	0.785±0.31	25.60±1.1	14.71±1.21	1.16±0.02
ADII	0.660±0.03	0.774±0.43	25.07±1.6	15.42±1.51	1.19±0.03
ADIII	0.656±0.02	0.741±0.24	24.68±1.5	14.03±1.15	1.15±0.05
ADC	0.725±0.03	0.776±0.01	23.94±1.6	14.47±1.51	1.14±0.03
AHC	0.690±0.05	0.734±0.03	25.73±1.1	12.42±1.23	1.10±0.05

Post-compression Parameters:

Hardness:

The hardness of all the prepared tablets was maintained within the 6.5±0.10 kg/cm² to 7.0±0.30 kg/cm². The mean hardness test results are shown in table no. 6.

Thickness:

The mean thickness was (n=3) almost uniform in all the formulations and values ranged from 4.43±0.009 mm to 4.64±0.003 mm. The standard deviation values indicated that all the formulations were within the range. The results of thickness for tablets were shown in table no. 6.

Weight variation test:

The weight variation was found in all designed formulations in the range 298±0.45 mg to 301±0.65mg. The mean weight variation test results are shown in table no. 6.

All the tablets passed weight variation test as the

average percentage weight variation was within 7.5 % i.e. in the pharmacopoeial limits.

Friability test:

The friability was found in all designed formulations in the range 0.5±0.003 to 0.80.002% to be well within the approved range (<1%). The friability study results were tabulated in table no. 6.

Drug Content:

The drug content uniformity was performed for all the formulations and results are tabulated in table no. 6. Three trials from each batch were analyzed spectrophotometrically. The average value and standard deviations of all the formulations were calculated. The percentage drugs content of the tablets were found to be between 95.51±1.75 to 100.03±1.23 % of Aceclofenac. The results were within the range and that indicated uniformity of mixing.

Table 6: Post-compressional parameters Aceclofenac Matrix Tablets.

Formulation Code	Parameter				
	Hardness (kg/cm ²) ±SD,n=3	Thickness (mm) ±SD,n=3	Weight Variation(mg) ±SD,n=3	Friability (%) ±SD,n=3	Drug Content (%) ±SD,n=3
AC I	7.0±0.09	4.64±0.003	301±0.47	0.6±0.005	97.43±1.23
AC II	7.0±0.30	4.58±0.002	300±0.75	0.5±0.003	98.12±1.19
AC III	6.5±0.23	4.49±0.009	299±0.23	0.6±0.006	97.38±1.62
AHI	7.0±0.10	4.54±0.009	299±1.50	0.6±0.001	96.65±1.20
AHII	6.5±0.31	4.49±0.003	298±0.45	0.8±0.002	99.65±1.42
AHIII	6.5±0.20	4.63±0.005	301±0.65	0.7±0.004	95.61±0.94
ADI	6.5±0.26	4.63±0.003	301±0.58	0.6±0.006	96.61±1.32
ADII	6.5±0.19	4.57±0.008	299±0.39	0.6±0.008	97.43±1.27
ADIII	7.0±0.13	4.45±0.007	301±0.47	0.7±0.001	95.51±1.75
ADC	6.5±0.23	4.54±0.002	299±0.28	0.6±0.007	98.65±1.28
AHC	7.0±0.09	4.49±0.005	301±0.14	0.7±0.003	99.43±1.03

IN-VITRO RELEASE STUDY

The release of Aceclofenac from fast releasing layer was analyzed by plotting the percent drug release Vs time. It shows initial burst effect was shown, from all the formulations over 21 % of Aceclofenac was released within two hrs of dissolution study.

The formulation ACI, AC II and ACIII shows 91.35% drug release within 10 hrs. 91.94% within 12 hrs. and 81.34% within 12hrs. respectively.

The formulation ACI, AC II and AC III contains 32 %, 40 %, 48 % CMC respectively.

Formulation prepared with 32% of CMC were able to control the release of drug up to 10 hrs. only. When CMC concentration was increased to 40% and 48% it was able to control the release for another two hours only.

All the formulation prepared by using CMC as release retardant were failed to control the release up to 24 hrs.

The formulation AHI, AHII and AHIII shows 98.82 % drug release within 12 hrs. 99.25 % within 24 hrs and 88.82% within 24 hrs. respectively. The formulation AH I, AH II and AH III contains 32 %, 40 %, 48 % HPMC respectively.

Formulations fabricated with 32% of HPMC (AHI) were able to control the release of drug up to 12 hrs only. When HPMC concentration increased to 40%, it yielded as best formulation because it released 99.25 % of drug at the end of 24th hrs. When the concentration increased to 48%, at the end of 24th hr dissolution study, it released only

88.82 % of drug. It may be due to the formation of more viscous gel around the tablet matrix.

The formulation ADI, ADII and AD III shows 98.34% drug release within 24hrs. 77.20% within

24 hrs. and 69.12% within 24 hrs. respectively.

The formulation AD I, AD II and AD III contains 32 %, 40 %, 48 % Delonix regia seed gum. When tablets manufactured natural gum, with only 30% was enough to control the drug release up to 24 hrs. It was released around 98.34%, so it emerged as the most promised formulation. This natural gum with less concentration it enough to form the more viscous gel then CMC and HPMC. It was again confirmed by increasing the gum concentration to 40% and 48 %.

With 40% gum (AD II) only 72.20% drug was released at end of 24 hrs. and 69.12% with 48% (AD III).

The formulation ADC, AHC shows 92.35 % drug release within 18 hrs., 98.70 % within 24 hrs. respectively.

Formulation fabricated by using CMC as release retardant polymer, were completely failed to control the release up to 24 hrs., so 24% CMC was mixed with 24% DRSG (formulation ADC) to study the improvement in characteristics of CMC. Formulation ADC was finally emerged as new promising formulation by releasing the drug of 92.35% at the end of 18hrs. But at the end of 18th hrs. CMC was failed to maintain the tablet consistency, so dissolution was stopped.

When formulation prepared by 24% HPMC mixed with 24% DRS gum (formulation AHC) were shows the drug release of 98.70% at the end of 24 hrs. It may be due to the combined viscous effect of both HPMC and DRS gum.

Table no.7:*In-vitro* drug release profile of Aceclofenac matrix tablet from ACI formulation.

S. No	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative % drug release	Log cumulative %drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	10.42	1.01786	89.58	1.9522
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	18.38	1.2643	81.62	1.9117
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	29.85	1.4749	70.15	1.8460
4	4	2	0.6020	39.07	1.5918	60.93	1.7848
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	47.08	1.6728	52.92	1.7236
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	56.55	1.7524	43.45	1.6379
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	65.88	1.8187	34.12	1.5330
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	76.63	1.8843	23.37	1.3686
9	9	3	0.9542	84.32	1.9259	15.68	1.1953
10	10	3.1622	1	91.35	1.9607	8.65	0.9370

Table no. 8:*In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from ACII formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative %drug release	Log cumulative %drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	9.6	0.9822	90.4	1.9561
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	17.62	1.2460	82.38	1.9158
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	27.37	1.4372	72.63	1.8611
4	4	2	0.6020	36.89	1.5669	63.11	1.8000
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	44.12	1.6446	55.88	1.7472
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	52.24	1.7180	47.76	1.6790
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	60.95	1.7849	39.05	1.5916
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	68.96	1.8385	31.04	1.4919
9	9	3	0.9542	75.52	1.8780	24.48	1.3888
10	10	3.1622	1	81.59	1.9116	18.41	1.2650
11	11	3.3166	1.0413	86.49	1.9369	13.51	1.1306
12	12	3.4641	1.0791	91.94	1.9635	8.06	0.9063

Table no.9:*In-vitro* drug release profile of Aceclofenac matrix tablet from AC III formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative %drug release	Log cumulative %drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	11.15	1.0472	88.85	1.9486
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	18.97	1.2780	81.03	1.9086
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	26.72	1.4268	73.28	1.8649
4	4	2	0.6020	34.61	1.5392	65.39	1.8155
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	40.14	1.6035	59.86	1.7771
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	48.71	1.6876	51.29	1.7100
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	55.8	1.7466	44.2	1.6454
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	61.94	1.7919	38.06	1.5804
9	9	3	0.9542	68.4	1.8350	31.6	1.4996
10	10	3.1622	1	73.53	1.8664	26.47	1.4227
11	11	3.3166	1.0413	77.08	1.8869	22.92	1.3602
12	12	3.4641	1.0791	81.34	1.9103	18.66	1.2709

Table no10: Kinetic data of formulations of Matrix tablets of Aceclofena (ACI, AC II, AC III).

Formulation Code	R ² Zero Order	R ² First Order	R ² Higuchi equation	R ² Peppas equation
ACI	0.998	0.801	0.991	0.998
ACII	0.992	0.819	0.991	0.997
ACIII	0.990	0.801	0.981	0.998

Fig.5:Higuchi plot for formulation ACI,ACII,AC III.

Fig.6:Peppas plot for formulation ACI,ACII,AC III.

Table no. 11:*In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from AH I formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative % drug release	Log cumulative % drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	11.31	1.053	88.69	1.9478
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	21.07	1.3236	78.93	1.8972
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	30.14	1.4791	69.86	1.8442
4	4	2	0.6020	39.27	1.5940	60.73	1.7834
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	47.6	1.6776	52.4	1.7193
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	55.26	1.7424	44.74	1.6506
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	64.05	1.8065	35.95	1.5556
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	72.28	1.8590	27.72	1.4427
9	9	3	0.9542	78.53	1.8950	21.47	1.3318
10	10	3.1622	1	85.34	1.9311	14.66	1.1661
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	92.12	1.9643	7.88	0.8965
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	98.82	1.9948	1.18	0.0718

Table no. 12:*In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from AH II formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative % drug release	Log cumulative % drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	10.96	1.03981	89.04	1.9495
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	17.97	1.25454	82.03	1.9139
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	26.51	1.4234	73.49	1.8662
4	4	2	0.6020	32.73	1.5149	67.27	1.8278
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	38.07	1.5805	61.93	1.79190
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	45.55	1.6584	54.45	1.7359
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	50.51	1.7033	49.49	1.6945
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	54.93	1.7398	45.07	1.6538
9	9	3	0.9542	59.39	1.7737	40.61	1.6086
10	10	3.1622	1	62.55	1.7962	37.45	1.5734
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	67.05	1.8263	32.95	1.5178
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	71.43	1.8538	28.57	1.4559
13	18	3.6836	1.1468	89.14	1.9500	10.86	1.0358
14	24	3.8557	1.1957	99.25	1.9967	0.75	-0.1249

Table no.13:*In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from AH III formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative % drug release	Log cumulative % drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	10.83	1.0346	89.17	1.9502
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	18.11	1.2579	81.89	1.9132
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	24.78	1.3941	75.22	1.8763
4	4	2	0.6020	28.36	1.4527	71.64	1.8551
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	32.68	1.5142	67.32	1.8281
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	37.4	1.5728	62.6	1.7965
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	40.12	1.6033	59.88	1.7772
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	45.38	1.6568	54.62	1.7373
9	9	3	0.954	49.46	1.6942	50.54	1.7036
10	10	3.1622	1	53.61	1.7292	46.39	1.6664
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	55.48	1.7441	44.52	1.6485
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	61.26	1.7871	38.74	1.588
13	18	3.6836	1.1468	78.67	1.8958	21.33	1.3289
14	24	3.8557	1.1957	88.82	1.9485	11.18	1.0484

Table no 14: Kinetic data of formulations of Matrix tablets of Aceclofenac (AH I, AH II, AH III).

Formulation Code	R ² Zero Order	R ² First Order	R ² Higuchi equation	R ² Peppas equation
AH I	0.994	0.885	0.952	0.999
AH II	0.992	0.878	0.985	0.989
AH III	0.948	0.986	0.984	0.997

Fig.8:First order *in-vitro* release profile for formulation AH I,AH II,AH III.

Fig.9:Higuchi plot for formulation AH I,AH II,AHIII.

Fig.10:Peppas plot for formulation AH I,AH II,AH III.

Table no. 15: *In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from ADI formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative %drug release	Log cumulative %drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	11.26	1.0515	88.74	1.9481
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	19.17	1.2826	80.83	1.9075
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	26.67	1.4260	73.33	1.8652
4	4	2	0.6020	32.45	1.5112	67.55	1.8296
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	38.61	1.5867	61.39	1.7880
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	43.71	1.6405	56.29	1.7504
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	48.84	1.6887	51.16	1.7089
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	53.21	1.7259	46.79	1.6701
9	9	3	0.9542	58.18	1.7647	41.82	1.6213
10	10	3.1622	1	62.21	1.7938	37.79	1.5773
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	66.13	1.8203	33.87	1.5298
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	70.79	1.8499	29.21	1.4655
13	18	3.6836	1.1468	87.47	1.9418	12.53	1.0979
14	24	3.8557	1.1957	98.34	1.9927	1.66	0.2201

Table no. 16: *In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from AD II formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative %drug release	Log cumulative % drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	10.17	1.0073	89.83	1.9534
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	18.55	1.2683	81.45	1.9108
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	22.24	1.3471	77.76	1.8907
4	4	2	0.6020	25.87	1.4127	74.13	1.8699
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	28.87	1.4604	71.13	1.8520
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	32.64	1.513	67.36	1.8284
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	36.92	1.5672	63.08	1.7998
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	40.87	1.6114	59.13	1.7718
9	9	3	0.9542	44.32	1.6466	55.68	1.7456
10	10	3.1622	1	48.21	1.6831	51.79	1.7142
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	51.17	1.7090	48.83	1.6886
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	54.78	1.7386	45.22	1.6553
13	18	3.6836	1.1468	69.09	1.8394	30.91	1.4900
14	24	3.8557	1.1957	77.20	1.8876	22.8	1.3579

Table no.17: *In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from AD III formulation.

S. No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative % drug release	Log cumulative %drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	10.31	1.0132	89.69	1.9527
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	18.05	1.2564	81.95	1.9135
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	21.07	1.3236	78.93	1.8972
4	4	2	0.6020	23.38	1.3688	76.62	1.8843
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	26.22	1.4186	73.78	1.8679
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	29.31	1.4670	70.69	1.8493
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	31.38	1.4966	68.62	1.8364
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	34.8	1.5415	65.2	1.8142
9	9	3	0.954	37.76	1.5770	62.24	1.7940
10	10	3.1622	1	40.06	1.6027	59.94	1.7777
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	42.17	1.6250	57.83	1.7621
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	45.64	1.6593	54.36	1.7352
13	18	3.6836	1.1468	59.14	1.7718	40.86	1.6112
14	24	3.8557	1.1957	69.12	1.8396	30.88	1.4896

Table no18: Kinetic data of formulations of Matrix tablets of Aceclofenac (ADI, ADII, ADIII)

Formulation Code	R ² Zero Order	R ² First Order	R ² Higuchi equation	R ² Peppas equation
ADI	0.926	0.915	0.996	0.993
ADII	0.937	0.996	0.993	0.993
ADIII	0.950	0.993	0.990	0.991

Fig.11:Zero order *in-vitro* release profile for formulation ADI,AD II,ADIII.

Fig.12:First order *in-vitro* release profile for formulation ADI,AD II,AD III

Fig.13:Higuchi plot for formulation AD I,AD II,ADIII.

Fig.14:Peppas plot for formulation ADI,AD II,AD III.

Table no.19:*In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from ADC formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative %drug release	Log cumulative % drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	12.75	1.1055	87.25	1.9407
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	19.63	1.2929	80.37	1.9050
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	26.04	1.4156	73.96	1.8689
4	4	2	0.6020	31.38	1.4966	68.62	1.8364
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	37.56	1.5747	62.44	1.7954
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	43.69	1.6403	56.31	1.7505
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	49.97	1.6987	50.03	1.6992
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	54.06	1.7328	45.94	1.6621
9	9	3	0.9542	58.57	1.7676	41.43	1.6173
10	10	3.1622	1	63.2	1.8007	36.8	1.5658
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	67.5	1.8293	32.5	1.5118
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	70.21	1.8463	29.79	1.4740
13	18	3.6836	1.1468	92.35	1.9654	7.65	0.8836

Table no.20:*In-vitro* drug release profile of aceclofenac matrix tablet from AHC formulation.

S.No.	Time in hr	Square root of time	Log time	Cumulative %drug release	Log cumulative % drug release	Cumulative % drug remaining	Log cumulative % drug remaining
1	1	1	0	11.44	1.058426	88.56	1.947238
2	2	1.4142	0.3010	18.32	1.2629	81.68	1.9121
3	3	1.7320	0.4771	23.56	1.3721	76.44	1.8833
4	4	2	0.6020	28.95	1.4616	71.05	1.8515
5	5	2.2360	0.6989	31.97	1.5047	68.03	1.8327
6	6	2.4494	0.7781	36.27	1.5595	63.73	1.8043
7	7	2.6457	0.8450	40.06	1.6027	59.94	1.7777
8	8	2.8284	0.9030	44.39	1.6472	55.61	1.7451
9	9	3	0.9542	48.34	1.6843	51.66	1.7131
10	10	3.1622	1	53.98	1.7322	46.02	1.6629
11	11	3.3394	1.0493	57.81	1.7620	42.19	1.6252
12	12	3.5115	1.0978	60.04	1.7784	39.96	1.6016
13	18	3.6836	1.1468	82.28	1.9152	17.72	1.2484
14	24	3.8557	1.1957	98.7	1.9943	1.3	0.1139

Table no 21: Kinetic data of formulations of Matrix tablets of Aceclofenac (ADC,AHC).

Formulation Code	R ² Zero Order	R ² First Order	R ² Higuchi equation	R ² Peppas equation
ADC	0.980	0.938	0.994	0.998
AHC	0.988	0.938	0.985	0.997

Fig.15:Zero order *in-vitro* release profile for formulation ADC,AHC.

Fig.16:First order *in-vitro* release profile for formulation ADC,AHC.

Fig.17:Higuchi plot for formulation ADC,AHC.

Fig.18:Peppas plot for formulation ADC,AHC.

RESULTS FOR DRUG POLYMER INTERACTION BY FTIR.

The characteristic absorption peaks of Aceclofenac is at 3425cm^{-1} is due to amino group. The peak at 1687cm^{-1} is due to presences of carbonyl group (present in the cytidine). The peak at 1258cm^{-1} and 1141cm^{-1} owing to asymmetrical stretching of c-o-c system (present in the oxathiolane ring). All these peaks were also present in the drug +HPMC mixture, drug+ CMC mixture, and drug + delonix regia seed gum mixture it indicates that drug was retained its identity without losing its characteristics. These findings were further supported by DSC study.

DSC STUDIES:

DSC thermo gram of pure aceclofenac showed a sharp melting endothermic peak at 176.6c , drug + HPMC, Drug + CMC and Drug + Delonixregia seed

gum showed the melting points at 177.8 , 175.5 , and 176.5 respectively indicating negligible change. This result demonstrates that there is no interaction between drug and excipients.

Result of stability study:

Stability study was done on only promising formulations viz AHII, ADI, AHC, and ADC, with target of drug content. At end of one month all the promised formulations were checked for their drug content in triplicate and noticed negligible change in the drug content. Similarly at the end of 2nd month again all formulations were evaluated the drug content and again same result was noticed. Finally at end of 3rd month again all formulations drug content were determined any very negligible change in the drug content were noticed.

Table 22: Drug Content Data after Stability studies

S.No.	Formulation code	1 st day	30 th day	60 th day	90 th day
1	AHII	99.65±1.42	99.12±1.19	98.62±1.82	98.14±1.28
2	ADI	96.61±1.32	95.61±0.94	95.65±1.20	95.60±1.75
3	AHC	99.43±1.03	99.42±1.82	99.21±1.45	99.22±1.19
4	ADC	98.65±1.42	98.61±1.45	98.40±1.03	98.60±1.82

CONCLUSION:

In the present work sustained release tablets of Aceclofenac were prepared by wet granulation methods, using synthetic and natural polymer like CMC, HPMC and Delonix regia seed gum.

All the Matrix tablets of Aceclofenac were subjected to hardness, weight variation, friability, drug content uniformity, *in-vitro* drug release, drug polymer interaction study.

The above studies lead to following conclusions:

- The Matrix tablets were prepared by wet granulation method.
- The prepared tablets were found to be good and free from chipping and capping.
- The hardness of the prepared tablets was found to be in the range of 6.5Kg/cm^2 to 7.0Kg/cm^2 .
- The low values of the standard deviation of average weight of the prepared tablets indicate weight uniformity within the batches prepared.
- The friability values of the prepared tablet were found to be less than 1%.
- The percentage drug content was uniform in all the formulations of prepared Matrix tablets.

- The effect of polymer on the *in-vitro* drug release behavior was significant.
- Formulation AH II, AD I, ADC and AHC shows better sustained release when compare to the other batches and indicates the ideal polymer and excipients percentage.
- IR spectroscopic and DSC studies indicated that the drug is compatible with all the excipients.
- The stability study shows that no significant changes in drug content month study.
- The polymer CMC was failed to control the drug release up to 24 hrs. at any concentration.
- The formulation prepared by using HPMC at 32 % was again failed to retain the drug release up to desired time. Its concentration increased to 40% (AHII) controlled the drug release up to 24hrs. But its concentration again increased to 48% (AHIII) was released only 88.82% drug at the end of 24 hrs.
- When formulation planned to prepare with natural gum (DRSG), only 32% was enough to control the release of drug up to 24% hrs. (AD I). When concentration increased to 40% (AD II) and 48 % (AD III), only 72.20 % and 69.12 % drug was release at the end of 24 hrs.
- Formulations ADC (24 % CMC and 24 %

DRSG) and AHC (24% HPMC and 24% DRSG) was formulated by mixing both natural and synthetic polymers. When CMC was incorporated with DRSG it leads to release the drug up to 18 hrs. Formulation with HPMC and DRSG it released the drug at the end of 24 hrs by releasing 98.70%.

- Based on the observations, it can be concluded that the formulated sustained release matrix tablets of aceclofenac using HPMC and DRSG were capable of exhibiting sustained release properties. They are thus reducing the dose intake, minimize the blood level oscillation, dose related adverse effect, cost and ultimately improve the patient compliance and drug efficiency.

SUMMARY

The present work was an attempt to develop novel sustained release Matrix tablets of Aceclofenac which is used in treatment of muscle spasm.

The formulation known as Matrix tablet was developed with the aim to deliver the Aceclofenac as conventional tablet and extend the drug release for 24 hrs for the better and extended clinical effect. The *In-vitro* drug release study was performed to study the effect of dosage form factor. Aceclofenac was chosen as the model drug, as its shelf life is 4hrs and to overcome the limitation of the conventional oral dosage form i.e. oscillation of plasma drug concentration and frequent administration. Thus, the formulations were prepared to reduce the side effects, increase the clinical effect and subsequently lower the dose and cost of the treatment.

The result of the drug-excipient compatibility studies revealed that there was no chemical interaction between the pure drug and excipients. The physical mixture of immediate release layer and the sustained release layer were subjected to flow property tests. The physical mixture of sustained release layer equivalent to 100 mg of drug was compressed into matrix tablets by wet granulation method. The tablet formulations were subjected to various tests such as thickness, hardness, friability, weight variation, drug content and *in-vitro* drug release profile in pH 1.2 buffers and pH 7.4 buffers.

From the data obtained from the *In-vitro* release profile, it was observed that, the formulation containing 40% HPMC, 32% DRSG, mixture 24% each of CMC and DRSG and 24 % each of HPMC and DRSG having formulation code AHII, ADI, ADC, and AHC respectively shows desired drug release rate. Hence these formulations were subjected

to stability studies.

From the stability studies, it was observed that there were no significant changes in the physical properties and drug content of the formulations and therefore the formulations are quite stable.

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